

The Role of Work Motivation, Work Environment and Member Performance in Military District Command

Budi Santoso¹, Boge Triatmanto², Sunardi³

^{1,2,3} University of Merdeka Malang

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
21 June 2024

Corresponding Author:
Sunardi

ABSTRACT

This research aims to examine transformational leadership, work motivation, and work environment on performance through job satisfaction. This research was conducted in Military District Command, East Java. This research population shows specific characteristics that can be used to conclude the thesis. The population of this study were members of the lower ranks in the army, with a population of 527 people. Based on the notation of the minimum research sample size formula by Slovin above, a sample of 181 can be determined.

Descriptive analysis can be carried out to assess characteristics using descriptive statistics such as mean, median, mode, standard deviation, variance, etc. The research results show that personnel motivation creates a positive and inclusive work environment. Work motivation is driven by awareness of the importance of the mission, recognition from leadership, and growth opportunities. A good work environment is based on explicit norms, open communication, collaboration, and mutual respect. This increases the job satisfaction of personnel in military organizations. Support and cooperation between unit members at Military District Command are critical to achieving optimal performance and operational goals. Contribution Research is an essential reference in studying employee satisfaction and performance, especially in military organizations that employ top-down decisions—using the Structural Contingency Theory (SCT) theory.

KEYWORDS: Work Motivation, Work Environment

1. INTRODUCTION

The Performance evaluation is carried out continuously according to the organization's mission and goals. A good organization is an organization that develops and applies the principles of professionalism to provide satisfaction values. Performance improvement can be done through a process of accountable human resource practices. Human resource practices can increase work motivation (existence, relationships and growth) to create performance (Hendri, 2019).

The implementation of an organization is often faced with various obstacles and challenges that impact employee performance. The obstacles in question include the speed of change, developments in the work environment and limited human resources in the organization. Environmental developments can influence job satisfaction levels (Karsli & Iskender, 2009). This shows that the human resources (HR) environment is critical because humans have a main role in the organization.

The success or failure of an organization in maintaining its existence begins with managing human resources by empowering and maximizing existing leadership potential to be more productive in improving performance (Jaroliya & Gyanchandani, 2022). Borman (2004) stated that performance is a result that employees can achieve through the authority given to achieve the organization's vision, mission, and goals.

In the era of globalization, organizational leaders pay attention to ways to improve organizational performance and increase employee job satisfaction so that they want to work better for the organization. Until now, job satisfaction has been an exciting and vital issue to study because it significantly influences the interests of individuals, organizations, and society (Agbozo et al., 2017). Job satisfaction is essential for improving performance because it is a significant problem that must be solved to improve performance (Ali et al., 2016) continuously. With more and more employees performing well, overall organizational

productivity will increase so the organization can survive in global competition.

Employees must be able to complete their duties and responsibilities effectively and efficiently. Employee success can be measured through customer satisfaction, reducing the number of complaints, and achieving optimal targets (Brahmasari & Suprayetno, 2008). According to Anasi (2020), job satisfaction helps create positive employee attitudes, increases morale, improves performance, and creates pleasant relationships with coworkers. Employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to be more creative and innovative, which helps the business to grow, develop and bring positive changes according to the market situation. In this way, organizations can compete internationally (Hendri, 2019).

Based on the problems above, this research aims to:

Describe work motivation, work environment, job satisfaction, and performance and research contribution: It is hoped that this research can contribute to a better understanding of leadership styles theory in different conditions and situations, such as the human need for relationships with other people in the context of a leader who can provide inspiration and motivation. For the Indonesian Army

It is hoped that the results of this research can be input to Army Headquarters for the development and development of human resources at the Military District Command.

1.1 Literature Review

Structural Contingency Theory is one of the references underlying organizational performance theory. Structural Contingency Theory's central premise is that there is no one best organizational structure; rather, the appropriate organizational structure depends on the contingencies facing the organization Blau (1970). This theory argues that organizations will be effective if managers adapt their characteristics, such as their structure, to the contingencies in their environment. Organizational success does not mean adopting maximum levels, but rather appropriate levels of structural variables that depend on some contingency variables (Donaldson, 2001). An organization that has characteristics (e.g., needs, demands, goals, objectives, and structure) that match the contingencies in its situation will work more effectively compared to an organization whose characteristics do not match the contingencies in its situation (Nadler & Tushman, 1980)

Research by Chu & Lai (2011) states that performance is the quality of task- and work-oriented behavior. Meanwhile, according to Wan & Ong (2005), performance is the result of work achieved by a person or group of people in an organization by their respective authority and responsibilities in order to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, without violating the law and in accordance with morals and ethics.

Performance, according to "Robbins & Judge (2012; 555), is the result of the quality and quantity achieved by a person in carrying out his duties based on the responsibilities given to him. Thus, performance (work achievement) is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him."

Factors that influence employee performance, according to Kasmir (2016), are skills and abilities, as well as a person's skills in adapting to workers, and satisfaction factors at work because of feelings of like or happiness; someone's pleasure in carrying out a job can create a good performance. Employees feel happy or enjoy their work so that the results of their profession are successful. Moreover, another factor that influences performance is work motivation, which can include the comfort of the activity area, such as room, layout, tools and adequate infrastructure.

Good focus is essential for people to organize and maximize their abilities in carrying out activities or achieving goals. For Robert & John (2006), employee performance is success in achieving goals; there are three essential aspects, namely the employee's skills, which include ability, attention and character. Level of expertise is the material an employee possesses in the form of insight, description, expertise, interpersonal, and technical skills.

Work quality is the achievement of employee performance measured by the work results achieved by workers at work. Work quality can also be measured by output or work results compared to the output standards set by the organization. Operational performance is related to the effectiveness of each resource the organization uses and the ability to use the human resources that work on it.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.1 Research design

This research is included in the category of causal associative research using a quantitative approach. According to Sanusi (2011:14), causal associative research is designed to examine the possibility of a cause-and-effect relationship between variables. This research will explain the relationship between influencing and being influenced by the variables to be studied. According to Sugiyono (2018: 14) the definition of a quantitative method is a research method that is based on the philosophy of positivism and is used to research specific populations or samples; data collection uses research instruments; data analysis is quantitative or statistical to test hypotheses which have been previously determined.

2.2 Population and Sample

This research population shows specific characteristics that can be used to conclude the thesis. The population of this study were members of the lower ranks in the army, with a population of 527 people. Based on the minimum research sample size formula notation by Slovin above, a sample of 181 can be determined.

2.3 Data analysis technique

Descriptive analysis can be carried out to assess characteristics using descriptive statistics such as mean, median, mode, standard deviation, variance, etc.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the descriptive analysis show the frequency distribution of respondents' answers regarding feelings of motivation due to obtaining employee status. The majority of respondents stated that they strongly agreed with 110 respondents (60.4%), followed by 63 respondents (34.6%) who agreed and nine respondents (4.9%) who stated they were neutral. The average value of 4.55 shows that most respondents strongly agree that they feel motivated because they have obtained employee status.

Regarding feelings of motivation because they get guaranteed health services, the majority of respondents, 100 respondents (54.9%), said they agreed, followed by 55 respondents (30.2%) who said they strongly agreed, 23 respondents (12.6%) said they were neutral, four respondents (2.2%) said they disagreed, and no respondents said they strongly disagreed. The average value of 4.13 shows that most respondents agree that they feel motivated because they get health service guarantees.

The existence indicator has an average score of 4.34, which means that respondents strongly agree that the existence of members is appreciated positively by the majority of respondents. The statement of feeling motivated because of obtaining employee status is the most approved in describing existence indicators.

The distribution of respondents' answers or responses regarding feelings of motivation due to the support of fellow work members found that the majority of answers stated that they strongly agreed, namely 116 respondents (63.7%), followed by 57 respondents (31.3%) who agreed, and 9 respondents (4.9%) which states neutral. The average score of 4.59 shows that respondents strongly agree that they feel motivated because of the support of fellow work members.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding all members involved in decision-making showed that the majority of answers stated that they strongly agreed with 103 respondents (56.6%), followed by 70 respondents (38.5%) who agreed, and nine respondents (4.9%) who stated they were neutral. The average score of 4.52 indicates that respondents agree that all members are involved in decision-making intensely.

The relationship indicator has an average score of 4.55, which means that respondents tend to strongly agree that relationships are appreciated positively by the majority of respondents. The statement of feeling motivated because of the support of fellow work members is the most approved in describing relationships.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding feelings of motivation due to getting a promotion found that the

majority of responses were 74 respondents (40.7%), followed by 64 respondents (35.2%) who strongly agreed, and 44 respondents (24.2%) who said they were neutral. The average score of 4.11 indicates that respondents agree that they feel motivated because they received a promotion.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding feelings of motivation due to getting a better career path was obtained by the majority of answers agreeing with 95 respondents (52.2%), followed by 64 respondents (35.2%) agreeing, and 23 respondents (12.6%) stating neutral. The average score of 4.23 shows that respondents strongly agree that they feel motivated because they are getting a better career path.

The growth indicator has an average score of 4.17, which means that most respondents agree that growth is appreciated positively by most respondents. The respondent's statement that they feel motivated because they have gotten a better career path is most agreed upon when describing growth.

The overall average work motivation score is 4.35; this shows that most respondents' perceptions strongly agree with work motivation, which consists of existence, relationships and growth. The dominant statement of respondents' perceptions regarding work motivation is that respondents feel motivated because of the support of fellow work members.

The results of the frequency distribution of respondents' answers regarding the ability of members to work together in realizing the vision. The majority of respondents stated that they agreed, as many as 103 respondents (56.6%), followed by 71 respondents (39.0%) who said they strongly agreed, and eight respondents (4.4%) said they were neutral. The average value of 4.35 shows that most respondents strongly agree that, as members, they can work together to realize the vision.

Regarding the requirement for members to solve problems together with other members, the majority of respondents, 95 respondents (52.2%), stated that they strongly agreed, followed by 82 respondents (45.1%) who agreed, and 5 respondents (2.7%) declared neutral. The average value of 4.49 shows that most respondents strongly agree that members must be able to solve problems together with other members.

The teamwork collaboration indicator has an average score of 4.42, meaning that respondents strongly agree that teamwork collaboration is appreciated positively by the majority of respondents. The statement that, as a member, I have to solve problems together with other members is most agreed upon when describing collaborative teamwork.

The distribution of respondents' answers or responses regarding equal equality between members in the organization found that the majority of answers stated agree, namely 102 respondents (56.0%), followed by 75 respondents (41.2%) who strongly agreed, and five respondents (2.7%) which states neutral. The average score of 4.38 shows that respondents strongly agree that there is equal equality between organization members.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding members getting equal opportunities in their careers showed that the majority of answers stated that they agreed, as many as 98 respondents (53.8%), followed by 79 respondents (43.4%) who strongly agreed, and five respondents (2.7%) who said neutral. The average score of 4.41 shows that respondents strongly agree that, as members, they get equal career opportunities.

The fair leadership indicator has an average score of 4.40, which means that respondents strongly agree that fair leadership is appreciated positively by most respondents. The statement that members have equal opportunities in their careers is most agreed upon in describing fair leadership.

The distribution of respondents' responses related to synergistic interactions with external parties in the organization was formed. The majority of responses were 102 respondents (56.0%), followed by 71 respondents (39.0%) who strongly agreed, and nine respondents (4.9%) who stated neutral. The average score of 4.34 indicates that respondents strongly agree that synergistic interactions have been formed with external parties to the organization.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding the existence of synergistic interactions with the community obtained that the majority of answers stated agree, with 103 respondents (56.6%), followed by 74 respondents (40.7%) who strongly agreed, and five respondents (2.7%) who stated they were neutral. The average score of 4.38 indicates that respondents strongly agree that the organization has synergistic social interactions.

The relationship indicator with stakeholders has an average score of 4.36, meaning that respondents strongly agree that most respondents positively appreciate relationships with stakeholders. The statement that there has been synergistic interaction with the community is most approved when describing relationships with stakeholders.

The average overall work environment score is 4.39; this shows that most respondents' perceptions strongly agree with work motivation: collaborative teamwork, fair leadership and relationships with stakeholders. The dominant perception statement of respondents in the work environment is the statement that members must solve problems together with other members.

Results of the frequency distribution of respondents' answers regarding the organization providing training. The majority of respondents stated that they agreed, as many as 104 respondents (57.1%), followed by 52 respondents (28.6%) who said they strongly agreed and 26 respondents (14.3%) who said they were neutral. The average value of 4.14 indicates that most respondents agree that the organization provides training.

Regarding organizations placing employees based on their skills, the majority of respondents, 114 respondents (62.6%), agreed, followed by 50 respondents (27.5%) who strongly agreed, and 18 respondents (9.9%) who disagreed—the

average value of 4.18 shows that most respondents agree that organizations place employees based on their skills.

The professional development indicator has an average score of 4.16, meaning that respondents tend to agree that most respondents positively appreciate professional development. Current organizational statements have placed employees based on the skills they possess most agreeably in describing professional development.

In the distribution of respondents' answers or responses regarding respect for superiors in the workplace, the majority of respondents agreed, namely 96 respondents (52.7%), followed by 71 respondents (39.0%) who strongly agreed, and 15 respondents (8.2%) who declared neutral. The average score of 4.31 shows that respondents strongly agree that there is respect for superiors in the workplace.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding superiors respecting subordinates in the workplace showed that the majority of answers stated that they agreed, with 96 respondents (52.7%), followed by 76 respondents (41.8%) who strongly agreed, five respondents (2.7%) who said they were neutral and five respondents (41.8%) who said they strongly agreed. 2.7% disagreed. The average score of 4.34 indicates that respondents strongly agree that superiors respect subordinates at work.

The indicator of working relationships with superiors has an average score of 4.32, which means that respondents tend to strongly agree that most respondents positively appreciate working relationships with superiors. The statement that the superior appreciates subordinates in the workplace is most approved in describing the working relationship with the superior.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding mutual respect for fellow members in the workplace showed that 90 respondents (49.5%) strongly agreed, followed by 87 respondents (47.8%) who agreed, and five respondents (2.7%) who said they were neutral. The average score of 4.47 indicates that respondents tend to agree that fellow members respect each other.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding communication between members is currently going well, with the majority of answers stating that they strongly agree, with 102 respondents (56.0%), followed by 66 respondents (36.3%) agreeing, and 14 respondents (7.7%) declaring neutral. The average score of 4.48 indicates that respondents strongly agree that communication between members is going well.

The indicator of working relationships with coworkers has an average score of 4.48, which means that respondents tend to strongly agree that working relationships with coworkers are appreciated positively by most respondents. The statement that communication between members is currently going well is most agreed upon when describing working relationships with colleagues.

The average overall job satisfaction score is 4.32, this shows that the majority of respondents' perceptions tend to strongly

agree that professional development leadership, working relationships with superiors and working relationships with colleagues are the primary forms of job satisfaction. The statement that contributes most to job satisfaction is that communication between members is going well.

Results of analysis of the frequency distribution of respondents' answers regarding members' responsibilities for the achievements of activity programs. The majority of respondents stated that they strongly agreed, with 95 respondents (52.2%), followed by 78 respondents (42.9%) who said they agreed and nine respondents (4.9%) who said they were neutral. The average value of 4.47 shows that the majority of respondents strongly agree that, as members, they are responsible for the achievements of the activity program. Regarding being a consistent member in administrative equipment activities, the majority of respondents, 93 respondents (51.1%), said they strongly agreed, followed by 84 respondents (46.2%) who agreed, and five respondents (2.7%) who said they were neutral. The average value of 4.48 shows that the majority of respondents strongly agree that members are consistent in administrative completeness.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding the activity program carried out as a member is relevant to the organization's goals. The majority of responses were 101 respondents (55.5%), followed by 66 respondents (36.3%) agreeing, and 15 respondents (8.2%)) stating neutral. The average score of 4.28 indicates that respondents agree that fellow members respect each other.

The activity program implementation indicator has an average score of 4.41, meaning that respondents strongly agree that the implementation of the activity program is appreciated positively by most respondents. The statement as a consistent member in administrative completeness activities is most approved in describing the implementation of the activity program.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding members being able to complete tasks based on the specified time showed that the majority of answers stated that they strongly agreed with 95 respondents (52.2%), followed by 82 respondents (45.1%) who agreed, and five respondents (2.7%) declared neutral. The average score of 4.49 shows that respondents strongly agree that they can complete tasks based on the specified time as members.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding members being able to complete work directly showed that the majority of answers stated that they agreed, with 87 respondents (47.8%), followed by 68 respondents (37.4%) who agreed, and 27 respondents (14.8%) who stated they were neutral. The average score of 4.23 indicates that respondents strongly agree that they can complete work directly as members.

The indicator for implementing individual activities has an average score of 4.36, meaning that respondents strongly agree that the implementation of individual activities is

appreciated positively by the majority of respondents. The statement that members can complete tasks based on the specified time is most agreed upon when describing the implementation of individual activities.

Regarding members having discipline in completing tasks, the majority of respondents, 89 respondents (48.9%), said they strongly agreed, followed by 88 respondents (48.4%) who agreed, and five respondents (2.7%) said they were neutral—the average value of 4.46 shows that most respondents strongly agree that members have discipline in completing tasks.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding members having speed in completing tasks found that the majority of respondents agreed, 88 respondents (48.8%), followed by 86 respondents (47.3%) who strongly agreed, and eight respondents (4.4%) who said they were neutral. The average score of 4.43 shows that respondents strongly agree that members can complete tasks quickly.

The distribution of respondents' responses related to being a member of acting reasonably in completing tasks found that the majority of responses stated that they strongly agreed with 97 respondents (53.3%), followed by 80 respondents (44.0%) who stated that they strongly agreed, and five respondents (2.7%) stated that neutral. The average score of 4.41 indicates that respondents strongly agree that, as members, they act reasonably in completing tasks.

The distribution of respondents' responses regarding members being polite in carrying out their duties showed that the majority of respondents strongly agreed, 97 respondents (53.3%), followed by 80 respondents (44.0%) who strongly agreed, and five respondents (2.7%) who said neutral. The average score of 4.51 indicates that respondents strongly agree that, as members, they behave politely in carrying out their duties.

The assignment quality indicator has an average score of 4.45, which means that respondents strongly agree that most respondents positively appreciate the quality of assignments. The statement that members behave politely in carrying out their duties is most approved when describing the quality of their assignments.

The overall average performance score is 4.41; this shows that most respondents' perceptions strongly agree with performance in implementing program activities, individual activities, and the quality of assignments. The dominant statement of respondents' perceptions regarding performance is that members behave politely in carrying out their duties.

4. DISCUSSION

Work motivation is one of the variables studied in this research. An overview of the description of the data resulting from the work motivation variable questionnaire statement is shown in Table 13. The indicators that reflect the work motivation variable in this research are existence, relationships and growth. Based on the analysis results Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), it was found that all the

indicators tested had loading factor values exceeding the cut-off value, meaning that the three indicators were able to form one factor or one latent variable, namely the work motivation variable.

Relations are the most significant indicator of work motivation based on descriptive analysis of the highest mean or average value. Having support from fellow work members or between members is a driving force in motivating them to carry out their duties and obligations. This indicates that members in the Military District Command work area tend to support each other. Support between fellow members creates a solid bond when working together to carry out tasks. As one of the institutions of the military public organization, it is an institution that demands total loyalty and commitment and is an organization that is designed as a solid force to work as efficiently as possible whenever the state needs it. In line with the descriptive analysis, empirically, the relationship indicator also has the highest average value compared to other indicators describing work motivation.

Next, the work motivation indicator provides the lowest contribution based on the analysis. The lowest average value is growth. This is determined by the motivation to get a better career path. To advance your career path in a military public organization, several years of service are required, and of course, each member must first undergo education as a condition for promotion. This indicates that members in the Military District Command work area perceive growth as not the main driver for carrying out their duties and obligations.

4.1 Work Environment

The work environment is one of the variables examined in this research. Descriptive analysis of data from questionnaire questions on work environment variables can be seen in Table 14. In this research, the work environment is reflected by collaborative teamwork, fair leadership and relationships with stakeholders. Based on the analysis results Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), it was found that all the indicators tested had loading factor values exceeding the cut-off value, meaning that the three indicators were able to form one factor or one latent variable, namely the work environment variable. The most significant contribution from indicators that reflect the work environment based on the results of the loading factors is teamwork collaboration. The results of the descriptive analysis also show that teamwork collaboration has the highest average value. This proves empirically that collaborative teamwork among members in the Military District Command work area is essential in forming a collaborative environment that allows for increased teamwork, especially in solving problems together to make everything run more smoothly so that it can contribute significantly to establishing a work environment at Military District Command.

The work environment indicator that provides the lowest contribution based on the loading factor results is the relationship with stakeholders. This result is in line with the

results of descriptive analysis, which also shows that relationships with stakeholders have the lowest average value. This indicates that members in the Military District Command work area perceive that relationships with stakeholders still need to be improved, especially synergistic interactions with parties external to the organization.

4.2 Performance

Performance is one of the variables examined in this research. Performance is defined as the quality and quantity of results a person achieves in carrying out tasks based on his responsibilities. Table 16 describes the data from the questionnaire questions on performance variables. Indicators that reflect performance variables include implementation of activity programs, implementation of individual activities and quality of assignments. From the results of the analysis Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), it was found that all the indicators tested had loading factor values exceeding the cut-off value, meaning that the three indicators were able to form one factor or one latent variable, namely the Performance variable.

The quality of assignments is the most significant contribution from indicators that reflect performance based on loading factor results. This result is in line with the results of the descriptive analysis, which also shows that the quality of assignments has the highest average value. This proves empirically that the quality of assignments to members in the Military District Command work area is essential for carrying out and completing tasks so that they can contribute significantly to the performance of members in the Military District Command work area.

Performance indicators that contribute based on the loading factor results are the implementation of individual activities. The results of the descriptive analysis also show that the implementation of individual activities has the lowest average value. This indicates that for members in the Military District Command work area, the implementation of individual activities has gone well but still needs to be improved. In this case, individual activities are implemented based on how members can complete tasks by following established procedures by their respective authorities and responsibilities to achieve organizational goals.

5. CONCLUSION

Motivate personnel and create a positive and inclusive work environment. Work motivation is driven by awareness of the importance of the mission, recognition from leadership, and growth opportunities. A good work environment is based on explicit norms, open communication, collaboration, and mutual respect. This increases the job satisfaction of personnel in military organizations. Support and cooperation between unit members at Military District Command are critical to achieving optimal performance and operational goals.

This research will be essential in studying employee satisfaction and performance, especially in military organizations that implement top-down decisions. Using Structural Contingency Theory (SCT), this research compares the success and failure of transplanting organizational structures from the private sector to the non-profit sector, considering the many criticisms of this theory. Military organizations must increase leadership training to motivate and inspire subordinates, manage conflict, and build effective teams. This will help provide clear direction and constructive feedback and ensure that each member feels heard and valued. Open communication between superiors and subordinates and developing a reward system for achievements are also essential to increase motivation and job satisfaction. The use of effective feedback and performance evaluation systems is necessary to identify areas for improvement.

REFERENCES

1. Adams, J. S. 1963. Towards an understanding of inequity. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 67, 422-436
2. Agbozo, G. K., Owusu, I. S., Hoedoafia, M. A., & Atakorah, Y. B. (2017). The Effect of Work Environment on Job Satisfaction: Evidence from the Banking Sector in Ghana. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 5(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jhrm.20170501.12>
3. Alderfer, C.P. (1972). *Existence, relatedness and growth*. New York: Free Press.
4. Ali, A., Bin, L. Z., Piang, H. J., & Ali, Z. (2016). The Impact of Motivation on the Employee Performance and Job Satisfaction in IT Park (Software House) Sector of Peshawar, Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 6(9), 297–310. <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v6-i9/2311>
5. Alrawahi, S., Sellgren, S. F., Altouby, S., Alwahaibi, N., & Brommels, M. (2020). The application of Herzberg’s two-factor theory of motivation to job satisfaction in clinical laboratories in Omani hospitals. *Heliyon*, 6(9), e04829.
6. Anasi, S.N. (2020), "Perceived influence of work relationship, work load and physical work environment on job satisfaction of librarians in South-West, Nigeria", *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, Vol. 69 No. 6/7, pp. 377-398.
7. Anh TT. (2017) The relationship between motivation and employee performance. Evidence from Ho Chi Minh City green product companies. *Ho Chi Minh City Open University Journal of Science*. 2017; 58(1): 41- 52.
8. Antonakis, J., Avolio, B.J. and Sivasubramaniam, N. (2003), “Context and leadership: an examination of the nine-factor full-range leadership theory using the multifactor leadership questionnaire”, *The Leadership Quarterly*, Vol. 14 No. 3, pp. 261-295.
9. Antonakis, J. and House, R.J. (2013), “The full-range leadership theory: the way forward”, in Avolio, B.J. and Yammarino, F.J. (Eds), *Transformational and Charismatic Leadership: The Road Ahead* 10th Anniversary Edition, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, Bingley, pp. 3-33.
10. Barry, Render dan Jay Heizer. 2001. *Prinsip-prinsip Manajemen Operasi : Operations Management*. Jakarta : Salemba Empat.
11. Bass, B.M. (1985), “*Leadership: good, better, best*”, *Organizational Dynamics*, Vol. 13 No. 3, pp. 26-40.
12. Bass, B.M. and Avolio, B.J. (1995), *MLQ: Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire* for Research: Permission Set, Mind Garden, Redwood City, CA.
13. Bass, B.M. and Avolio, B.J. (1997), *Full Range Leadership Development: Manual for the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire*, Mind Garden, Palo Alto, CA, pp. 43-44.
14. Bass, B.M. (1998), *Transformational Leadership: Industry, Military, and Education Impact*, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Mahawah, NJ. Bass, Bernard. & Avolio, Bruce., 2011, *Full range leadership development: Manual for multifactor leadership questionnaire*, Redwood City, California: Mind Garden
15. Blau, P. M. (1970). A formal theory of differentiation in organizations. *American Sociological Review*, 35, 201–218.
16. Boehnke, K., Bontis, N., DiStefano, J.J. and DiStefano, A.C. (2003), “Transformational leadership: an examination of cross-national differences and similarities”, *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 24 No. 1, pp. 5-15.
17. Borman WC. (2004) *The concept of organizational citizenship*. *Current directions in psychological science*. 2004; 13(6): 238-241.
18. Brahmasari dan Suprayetno (2008). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja, Kepemimpinan dan Budaya Organisasi terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan serta Dampaknya pada Kinerja Perusahaan, *Jurnal Manajemen dan Kewirausahaan Vol 10 No 2 September 2008*.
19. Burns, J.M. (1978), *Leadership*, Harper and Row Publishers, New York, NY.
20. Chang, S.C. and Lee, M.S. (2007), “A study on relationship among leadership, organizational culture, the operation of learning organization and employees’ job satisfaction”, *The Learning Organization*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 155-185.
21. Child, J. (1975). Managerial and organizational factors associated with company performance, part

- 2: A contingency analysis. *Journal of Management Studies*, 12, 12–27
22. Cao, G., Wiengarten, F., & Humphreys, P. (2011). Towards a contingency resource-based view of IT business value. *Systemic Practice and Action Research*, 24, 85–106.
- Deci, E. L., Olafsen, A. H., & Ryan, R. M. R. (2017). Self-Determination Theory in Work Organizations: The State of a Science. In *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior* (Vol. 4, pp. 19–43). The Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-032516-113108>
23. Donaldson, L. (2001). *The contingency theory of organizations*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
24. Eliyana, A., Ma'arif, S., & Muzakki. (2019). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment effect in the transformational leadership towards employee performance. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 25(3), 144–150.
25. ni, A. D. A., Martaleni, M., & Astuti, R. (2023). Pengaruh Kepemimpinan, Budaya Organisasi dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dengan kepuasan Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Economics And Business Management Journal (EBMJ)*, 2(01), 118-129.
26. Fernandez, S. (2008), “Examining the effects of leadership behavior on employee perceptions of performance and job satisfaction”, *Public Performance & Management Review*, Vol. 32 No. 2, pp. 175-205.
27. Greenwood, R., & Miller, D. (2010, November). Tackling design anew: Getting back to the heart of organizational theory. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 24(4), 78–88.
28. Ghozali, I. (2004). *Model Persamaan Struktural: Konsep dan Aplikasi dengan Program Amos 19.0*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
29. Ghozali, I. & Fuad. 2008. *Structural Equation Modeling: Teori, Konsep, dan Aplikasi Dengan Program Lisrel 8.80* (2th ed.). Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
30. Griffith, J. (2004), “Relation of principal transformational leadership to school staff job satisfaction, staff turnover, and school performance”, *Journal of Educational Administration*, Vol. 42 No. 3, pp. 333-356.
31. Hage, J. (1965). An axiomatic theory of organizations. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 10, 289–320.
32. Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B., Anderson, R. and Tatham, R. (2006) *Multivariate Data Analysis*. 6th Edition, Pearson Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River.
33. Harwika, W. (2016). The Impact of Servant Leadership on Organization Culture, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) and Employee Performance in Women Cooperatives. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 219, 283–290.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.04.032>
34. Hasan, H. (2019). Effect Of Work Experience And Work Environment On Job Satisfaction. *Bongaya Journal of Research in Management*, 2(1), 1–10.
35. Hendri, M. I. (2019). The mediation effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on the organizational learning effect of the employee performance. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 68(7), 1208–1234.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-05-2018-0174>
36. Herzberg F. (1959.) *The Motivation to Work*. New York: Wiley.
37. Herzberg F. (2003) *One More Time: How Do You Motivate Employees?* Harvard Business Review.
38. Hilton, S.K., Madilo, W., Awaah, F. and Arkorful, H. (2023), "Dimensions of transformational leadership and organizational performance: the mediating effect of job satisfaction", *Management Research Review*, Vol. 46 No. 1, pp. 1-19.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-02-2021-0152>
39. Isrokudin. (2022). Kerja Pada Construction & Engineering Department Petrochina International Jabung Ltd Kabupaten. *Jurnal Manajemen Terapan Dan Keuangan (Mankeu)*, 11(04), 890–903.
40. Indriasari, D. P., & Angreany. (2019). Pengaruh Locus Of Control Dan Beban Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Melalui Etos Kerja Pada Badan Pendapatan Daerah Provinsi Sulawesi Selatan. *Jurnal Of Management*
41. Jaroliya, D. and Gyanchandani, R. (2022), “Transformational leadership styles: a boost or a barrier to team performance in the IT sector”, *Vilakshan - XIMB Journal of Management*, Vol. 19 No.1, pp.87-105.
42. Kamery RH. Employee motivation as it relates to effectiveness, efficiency, productivity, and performance. In *Proceedings of the Academy of Legal, Ethical and Regulatory*. 2004; 8(2): 139-144.
43. Karsli, M. D., & Iskender, H. (2009). *To examine the effect of the motivation provided by the administration on the job satisfaction of teachers and their institutional commitment*. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 1(1), 2252–2257.
44. Lawrence, P., & Lorsch, J. (1967). Differentiation and integration in complex organizations. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 12, 1–30.
45. Lemma, N., Dugassa, E., & Temesgen, W. (2022). The Effect of Indoor Physical Work Environment on Employees Performance. *International Journal of*

- Current Research in Science Engineering & Technology*, 03 (March), 2582–5208. <https://doi.org/10.35248/2165-7556-22.12.295>.
46. Morton, N. A., & Hu, Q. (2008). Implications of the fit between organizational structure and ERP: A structural contingency theory perspective. *Information Management*, 28, 391–402.
 47. Moynihan, L.M., Boswell, W.R. and Boudreau, J.W. (2000), “The influence of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on executive withdrawal and performance”, CAHRS Working Paper No. 00-16, Cornell University, *School of Industrial and Labor Relations, Center for Advanced Human Resource Studies*, Ithaca, NY.
 48. Muriuki, L., & Mwengei Ombaba, K. B. (2018). Effect of Transformational Leadership on Organizational Performance of Micro Finance Institutions in Kenya. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences*, August, 88–100. <https://doi.org/10.47992/ijmts.2581.6012.0038>
 49. Nadler, D., & Tushman, M. (1980). A model for diagnosing organizational behavior. *Organizational Dynamics*, 9, 35–51
 50. Pawirosumarto, S., Sarjana, P.K. and Gunawan, R. (2017), "The effect of work environment, leadership style, and organizational culture towards job satisfaction and its implication towards employee performance in Parador Hotels and Resorts, Indonesia", *International Journal of Law and Management*, Vol. 59 No. 6, pp. 1337-1358.
 51. Perrow, C. (1967). A framework for the comparative analysis of organizations. *American Sociological Review*, 32, 194–208.
 52. Prabowo, Sanusi, Sumarsono. 2019. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja, Motivasi dan Stres Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. WIGA: *Jurnal Penelitian Ilmu Ekonomi*. Vol.8 No.1.
 53. Pugh, D. S., & Hinings, C. R. (1976). *Organizational structure: Extensions and replications: The Aston Programme II*. Farnborough, England: Saxon House.
 54. Puni, A., Mohammed, I., & Asamoah, E. (2018). Transformational leadership and job satisfaction: the moderating effect of contingent reward. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 39(4), 522–537. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-11-2017-0358>
 55. Rad, Mohammad Mosadegh A. and Hossein Yarmohammadian, M. (2006), “A study of relationship between managers’ leadership style and employees’ job satisfaction”, *Leadership in Health Services*, Vol. 19 No. 2, pp. 11-28.
 56. Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2012). *Organizational Behavior* (14th ed.). (Translation Editor: Inci Erdem). Ankara: Nobel Publications.
 57. Sahibzada, A., Tolossa, D. N., & Pandya, D. H. B. (2022). *The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction And The Performance Gap Interdisciplinarity The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction And The Performance Of Employees At Paktia University , Afghanistan. October.*
 58. Sanggarwati, D. A., Fitrianty, R., Tyas, W. S. A., & Kuswandi, K. (2021). Efek Kepemimpinan Transformasional Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Yang Berdampak Pada Kinerja Karyawan Di Pt. Citra Persada Infrastruktur Di Surabaya. *Media Mahardhika*, 19(2), 255–268. <https://doi.org/10.29062/mahardhika.v19i2.253>
 59. Sahibzada, A., Tolossa, D. N., & Pandya, D. H. B. (2022). The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction And The Performance Gap Interdisciplinarity The Relationship Between Job Satisfaction And The Performance Of Employees At Paktia University , Afghanistan. October.
 60. Sanusi Anwar. (2011). *Metode Penelitian Bisnis*. Jakarta: PT. Salemba Empat.
 61. Sedarmayanti. (2010). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Reformasi Birokrasi dan Manajemen Pegawai Negeri Sipil*. Bandung: Refika Aditama
 62. Siddique, A., Aslam, H.D., Khan, M. and Fatima, U. (2011), “Impact of academic leadership on faculty’s motivation, and organizational effectiveness in higher education system”, *International Journal of Academic Research*, Vol. 3 No. 3, pp. 730-737.
 63. Siddique, M. Z. (2020). the Relationship Between Music Teachers Work Motivation and Job Satisfaction. *International Journal of Eurasian Education and Culture*, 5(9), 698–744. <https://doi.org/10.35826/ijoecc.125>
 64. Sivanathan, N. and Cynthia Fekken, G. (2002), “Emotional intelligence, moral reasoning and transformational leadership”, *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 23 No. 4, pp. 198-204.
 65. Slovin, M.J., 1960. *Sampling*, Simon and Schuster Inc. New York
 66. Smith, W. K., & Lewis, M. W. (2011). Toward a theory of paradox: A dynamic equilibrium model of organizing. *Academy of Management Review*, 36, 381–403
 67. Sohail, A., Safdar, R., Saleem, S., Ansar, S., & Azeem, M. (2014). Effect of Work Motivation and Organizational Commitment on Job Satisfaction: (A Case of Education Industry in Pakistan). *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: A Administration and Management*, 14(6), 40–45.

<https://www.journalofbusiness.org/index.php/GJM/BR/article/view/1320/122>

68. Sugiyono. (2018) *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan: Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
69. Sullivan, E.J. and Decker, P.J. (2001), *Effective Leadership and Management in Nursing*, 5th ed., Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ.
70. Sumarwan, U. (2011). *Perilaku konsumen: Teori dan penerapannya dalam pemasaran*. Bogor: Ghalia Indonesia.
71. Sunyoto, Danang. 2015. *Manajemen dan Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia* (Cetakan Pertama). Yogyakarta: CAPS (Center for Academic Publishing Service).
72. Sürücü, L., Maslakçı, A. dan Sesen, H. (2022), "Transformational leadership, job performance, self-efficacy, and leader support: testing a moderated mediation model", *Baltic Journal of Management*, Vol. 17 No.4, hlm. 467-483.
73. Thang, D. Van, & Nghi, N. Q. (2022). The effect of work motivation on employee performance: the case at OTUKSA Japan company. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 13(1), 404–412. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.13.1.0047>
74. Thompson, J. (1967). *Organizations in action*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
75. Tucker, B. (2010). Through which lens? Contingency and institutional approaches to conceptualizing organizational performance in the not-for-profit sector. *Journal of Applied Management Accounting Research*, 8(1), 17–33.
76. Wreder Å, Gustavsson M, Klefsjö B. Management for sustainable health: A TQM-inspired model based on experiences taken from successful Swedish organizations. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*. 2008;25(6):561-84.
77. Woodward, J. (1965). *Industrial organization: Theory and practice*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
78. Yoghnan, Antoneta C. Laba, Abdul Rahman. Aswan, Andi. Balele, Bintang.2020. The Effect of Work Environment on Organizational Culture and Employees Performance The Case of Secretariats Office of Boven Digoel District. *Hasanuddin Journal of Business Strategy*. Vol.2 No.4